

THE IMPACT OF URBAN MUNICIPAL WASTE MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES ON THE ECONOMY OF ENUGU METROPOLITAN AREA, SOUTH EAST NIGERIA

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17366782>

Keywords,
Waste management, recycling, regulation enforcement, wealth creation, standard of living, Enugu Metropolis.

Abstract: *This study examined the impact of municipal waste management strategies on the economy of Enugu Metropolis, South-East Nigeria. The research was motivated by the growing challenges of rapid urbanization, population expansion, and inadequate waste management infrastructure that have contributed to environmental degradation and reduced economic opportunities in the city. A descriptive survey design was adopted, targeting a population of 913 staff of the Enugu State Waste Management Authority (ESWAMA). Using Freund and William's formula, a sample size of 271 respondents was selected, and data were obtained through structured questionnaires. Instrument validity was established through expert review, while reliability was confirmed with a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.91. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and Z-tests at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that recycling has a significant positive relationship with wealth creation in Enugu Metropolis, providing employment opportunities, reducing disposal costs, generating revenue from recyclables, and attracting green investments ($Z = 11.200, p < 0.05$). Similarly, regulation enforcement was found to significantly improve the standard of living, enhancing environmental quality, social cohesion, business fairness, and public health ($Z = 10.259, p < 0.05$). However, the study also identified key socioeconomic and institutional challenges that hinder effective waste management, including inadequate funding, weak enforcement, poor recycling facilities, low public awareness, and policy inconsistencies. The study concludes that waste management in Enugu Metropolis is both an environmental necessity and a potential economic driver. It recommends the establishment of modern recycling facilities, provision of tax incentives for recycling businesses, increased government and private sector funding, stricter regulation enforcement with stronger monitoring mechanisms, and the formalization of the informal recycling sector. Collectively, these strategies would reposition*

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waste management as a tool for sustainable economic growth, employment creation, and improved quality of life in Enugu Metropolis.

1. Introduction

Solid waste management has emerged as one of the most pressing environmental and socioeconomic challenges of the 21st century. Globally, the world generates about 2.01 billion tonnes of municipal solid waste each year, and this figure is projected to rise to 3.4 billion tonnes by 2050 if current trends persist (World Bank, 2018). More than one-third of this waste is not managed in an environmentally safe manner, with the highest levels of mismanagement occurring in low- and middle-income countries. The consequences include pollution of air, soil, and water, increased greenhouse gas emissions, and a decline in urban livability. Conversely, countries that have invested in efficient waste strategies, particularly in recycling and circular economy initiatives, have realized significant economic benefits. For instance, the European Union reported that the circular economy generated more than €147 billion in added value and provided about four million jobs in 2022 (Eurostat, 2023). These global experiences highlight that waste management is not only an environmental necessity but also a potential driver of sustainable economic development.

In Nigeria, which is Africa's most populous nation with an estimated population of 223 million (World Bank, 2023), the management of municipal solid waste has become increasingly complex. The country generates an estimated 32

million tonnes of waste annually, yet only about 20–30 percent is effectively collected and disposed of in an environmentally sound manner (UNEP, 2022). The composition of waste in Nigerian cities has also shifted over the past decades. While waste was predominantly biodegradable in the 1980s, recent studies indicate that plastics, metals, electronic waste, and other non-biodegradable materials now make up more than 40 percent of the urban waste stream (Ogunyemi et al., 2021). This change has increased the demand for recycling and advanced disposal methods, yet most municipalities rely heavily on open dumping, indiscriminate burning, and informal scavenging. These practices have been linked to environmental degradation, groundwater contamination, and frequent outbreaks of communicable diseases. At the same time, research has shown that with effective recycling and resource recovery programs, Nigeria's waste sector could generate over \$8 billion annually and create more than 200,000 new jobs, particularly in plastics, paper, and metal recycling industries (IFC, 2021).

The situation in Enugu Metropolis exemplifies these national challenges. Enugu, popularly known as the "Coal City," comprises Enugu North, Enugu South, and Enugu East local government areas and has a population estimated at more than 1.1 million (NPC, 2023).

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The rapid pace of urbanization, coupled with rising commercial and industrial activities, has significantly increased the volume and heterogeneity of waste produced. Despite the presence of the Enugu State Waste Management Authority (ESWAMA), which is mandated to oversee municipal waste collection and disposal, only about 40 percent of waste generated in the city is collected regularly (Ezemeribe, Umeh, & Eme, 2022). Studies further show that more than half of households—approximately 58 percent—experience delays of four days to over one week before waste is collected (Elekwachi, 2023). Recycling efforts remain minimal and are driven mainly by informal scavengers who operate without institutional support. As a result, illegal dumping along roadsides, clogged drains, and open-air burning of waste are widespread, aggravating flooding, poor sanitation, and declining air quality.

These inefficiencies represent both risks and opportunities for the city. On one hand, improper waste management contributes to public health hazards, environmental degradation, and reduced urban attractiveness for investors. On the other hand, if waste is strategically managed, it could provide new economic opportunities in recycling industries, create jobs for urban youth, improve environmental quality, and raise the overall standard of living for residents. Properly designed interventions such as tax incentives for recycling businesses, public-private partnerships for waste processing, and stricter enforcement of

sanitation laws could transform Enugu's waste problem into an engine of economic growth.

It is within this context that the present study investigates the impact of municipal waste management strategies on the economy of Enugu Metropolis. The research pursues three specific objectives: first, to examine the relationship between recycling and wealth creation in Enugu; second, to evaluate how regulation enforcement influences the standard of living of residents; and third, to identify the socioeconomic challenges that hinder effective waste management and propose strategies for leveraging waste as a tool for sustainable economic development. By addressing these objectives, the study contributes to ongoing policy discussions on how urban waste management in Nigeria can be repositioned as a catalyst for economic diversification, job creation, and sustainable urban development.

2. Methodology

2.1 Research Design

The study employed a descriptive survey research design, which is widely used in social and environmental sciences to obtain quantitative and qualitative information from a population regarding their attitudes, practices, and experiences (Kothari, 2014). This design was considered appropriate because it enabled the researcher to systematically collect, analyze, and interpret data from respondents on waste management practices and their economic implications within the Enugu Metropolis.

2.2 Study Area

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The research was conducted in Enugu Urban Metropolis, located in Enugu State, South-East Nigeria. The metropolis is made up of three Local Government Areas: Enugu North, Enugu South, and Enugu East. This area was chosen because it represents the political, commercial, and industrial hub of Enugu State and is also characterized by rapid urbanization, population growth, and rising waste generation. The Enugu State Waste Management Authority (ESWAMA) is the statutory agency responsible for waste collection, disposal, and environmental sanitation in the metropolis, making it the most relevant institution for the focus of this study (Ezemeribe, Umeh, & Eme, 2022).

2.3 Population of the Study

The target population consisted of 913 employees of ESWAMA, spread across four main categories: management staff, senior staff, field workers, and business men and women who interact directly with waste management operations. This population was deemed suitable because the staff and affiliated stakeholders are directly involved in the design, implementation, and enforcement of waste management strategies in Enugu Metropolis.

2.4 Sample Size Determination

A total sample size of 271 respondents was determined using Freund and William's statistical formula as cited by Uzoagulu (2009), with a 5% margin of error and a 95% confidence level. The formula ensured that the sample was representative of the entire population while maintaining statistical accuracy. To enhance

representativeness, the Bowley's proportional allocation formula was applied to distribute the sample across the different staff strata. This ensured that all categories of staff were adequately represented according to their numerical strength in the organization.

2.5 Sources of Data

The study relied on both primary and secondary data sources. The primary data were obtained through the administration of structured questionnaires. These questionnaires were designed on a five-point Likert scale (ranging from *strongly agree* to *strongly disagree*) to elicit responses on recycling practices, regulation enforcement, wealth creation, and standard of living. Secondary data were collected from relevant scholarly journals, textbooks, official reports, institutional records, and online publications on solid waste management in Nigeria and other developing countries (Agu, Nwankwoala, & Ogbuagu, 2019).

2.6 Validity and Reliability of Instrument

The content validity of the instrument was ensured through expert review. Specialists in environmental management and research methodology assessed the clarity, wording, and relevance of the questionnaire items. Their feedback was incorporated to refine the instrument. To test reliability, a pilot study was conducted using 20 ESWAMA staff outside the main sample. The data were analyzed using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, which returned a value of 0.91, surpassing the recommended threshold of 0.70 for social science research

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(George & Mallery, 2010). This indicates that the instrument was internally consistent and reliable for data collection.

2.7 Method of Data Collection

The researcher and trained assistants administered the questionnaires directly to respondents to ensure a high response rate. Out of the 271 questionnaires distributed, 254 were properly completed and returned, representing a 94% response rate. This high return rate enhanced the credibility and generalizability of the findings.

2.8 Method of Data Analysis

Data collected were coded, categorized, and entered into the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.0 for analysis. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, were used to summarize the responses. To test the hypotheses, inferential statistics were

employed, specifically the Z-test statistic, which is appropriate for examining the significance of differences between sample means and population parameters in large samples (Singh & Masuku, 2014). The decision rule was set at $p < 0.05$, which served as the benchmark for determining statistical significance.

3. Results

3.1 Objective One: Relationship between Recycling and Wealth Creation in Enugu Metropolis

The first objective of this study was to examine whether recycling has a significant relationship with wealth creation in Enugu Metropolis. Data were collected from 254 valid respondents using a five-point Likert scale. Table 3.1 presents the descriptive analysis of items measuring recycling initiatives and their perceived contribution to wealth creation.

Table 4.1: Respondents’ Perceptions of Recycling and Wealth Creation in Enugu Metropolis

S/N	Item Statement	SA (%)	A (%)	N (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Recycling initiatives in Enugu can create jobs in areas such as waste collection, sorting, and processing.	47.6	47.6	2.0	0.8	2.0	4.38	0.75	Agree
2	Recycling reduces pollution, preserves natural resources, and	44.5	49.6	2.0	1.6	2.4	4.32	0.80	Agree

	promotes a cleaner environment.								
3	Investment in recycling infrastructure attracts local and foreign investors in green technologies.	43.3	34.3	2.0	13.0	7.5	3.93	1.28	Agree
4	Innovative recycling technologies can make Enugu a hub for environmental tech businesses.	42.5	20.5	14.2	3.9	18.9	3.64	1.52	Agree
5	Recycling generates revenue through the sale of recycled raw materials.	56.3	20.5	5.1	3.5	14.6	4.00	1.44	Agree
Grand Mean						4.05	1.16	Agree	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The results indicate strong agreement among respondents that recycling is positively associated with wealth creation in Enugu Metropolis. Specifically: 95.2% of respondents agreed that recycling creates job opportunities in waste collection and processing (Mean = 4.38, SD = 0.75). 94.1% agreed that recycling reduces pollution and enhances environmental quality (Mean = 4.32, SD = 0.80). 77.6% recognized that investment in recycling infrastructure could attract local and foreign investors (Mean = 3.93). Although responses were more varied regarding whether innovative recycling technologies could

make Enugu a hub for environmental tech businesses, a majority (63.0%) still agreed. 76.8% agreed that recycling generates revenue through the sale of recycled raw materials (Mean = 4.00). The overall grand mean score of 4.05 (SD = 1.16) suggests a strong positive perception that recycling contributes to wealth creation in Enugu Metropolis.

Hypothesis Testing for Objective One

The hypothesis was tested using the One-Sample Kolmogorov–Smirnov Z-test to determine whether recycling has a statistically significant relationship with wealth creation.

Table 3.2: One-Sample Kolmogorov–Smirnov Test for Recycling and Wealth Creation

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Recycling Indicators	N	Z-Value	p-Value	Decision
Job creation through recycling	254	11.200	0.000	Significant
Pollution reduction & environmental preservation	254	11.012	0.000	Significant
Attraction of investments in green technologies	254	8.377	0.000	Significant
Innovation and tech-business opportunities	254	6.777	0.000	Significant
Revenue generation from recyclables	254	8.973	0.000	Significant

Source: SPSS Output, 2025

Decision Rule and Result

At $p < 0.05$, all items recorded Z-values ranging from 6.777 to 11.200, with p-values of 0.000. Since the calculated Z-values exceeded the critical values, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, the study accepts the alternative hypothesis that recycling has a significant positive relationship with wealth creation in Enugu Metropolis.

Relationship between Regulation Enforcement and Standard of Living in Enugu Metropolis

The second objective of this study was to determine whether regulation enforcement significantly influences the standard of living of residents in Enugu Metropolis. A total of 254 valid responses were analyzed. Table 3.3 presents the descriptive statistics of respondents' views.

Table 3.3: Respondents' Perceptions of Regulation Enforcement and Standard of Living

S/N	Item Statement	SA (%)	A (%)	N (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Regulation enforcement ensures businesses operate within legal boundaries, enhancing fair competition and preventing exploitation.	52.0	20.5	12.2	3.5	11.8	3.97	1.36	Agree
2	Enforcement of regulations that respect cultural heritage and promote social harmony leads to a more cohesive society.	40.9	26.8	5.1	2.0	25.2	3.56	1.62	Agree

3	Effective regulation enforcement improves public health and economic prosperity, contributing to a higher quality of life.	44.9	23.6	2.0	2.8	26.8	3.57	1.68	Agree
4	Proper enforcement of law and order (e.g., crime control, property rights protection, anti-corruption laws) improves safety and reduces crime.	26.4	29.9	2.0	15.0	26.8	3.14	1.60	Agree
5	Effective enforcement leads to cleaner air and better environmental quality, enhancing residents' well-being and the city's attractiveness.	38.6	50.8	2.0	1.2	7.5	4.12	1.06	Agree
Grand Mean						3.67	1.46	Agree	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The findings indicate that respondents overwhelmingly believe regulation enforcement positively influences standard of living in Enugu Metropolis. Specifically: 72.5% agreed that enforcement ensures fair competition and prevents exploitation in business practices (Mean = 3.97, SD = 1.36). 67.7% agreed that culturally sensitive enforcement promotes social cohesion (Mean = 3.56, SD = 1.62). 68.5% agreed that enforcement contributes to public health and prosperity (Mean = 3.57). Although responses were more mixed regarding crime

control and law enforcement, 56.3% still agreed it enhances safety (Mean = 3.14). The strongest agreement came from environmental quality: 89.4% agreed that enforcement leads to cleaner air and improved well-being (Mean = 4.12, SD = 1.06). The grand mean of 3.67 indicates a generally positive perception that regulation enforcement improves the standard of living.

Hypothesis Testing for Objective Two

The hypothesis was tested using the One-Sample Kolmogorov–Smirnov Z-test to establish statistical significance.

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Table 3.4: One-Sample Kolmogorov–Smirnov Test for Regulation Enforcement and Standard of Living

Regulation Enforcement Indicators	N	Z-Value	p-Value	Decision
Business fairness & anti-exploitation	254	8.282	0.000	Significant
Cultural heritage & social harmony	254	6.808	0.000	Significant
Public health & prosperity	254	7.153	0.000	Significant
Crime reduction & law enforcement	254	4.988	0.000	Significant
Environmental quality & clean air	254	10.259	0.000	Significant

Source: SPSS Output, 2025

At $p < 0.05$, all indicators of regulation enforcement recorded significant Z-values ranging from 4.988 to 10.259 with p-values of 0.000. Since the calculated Z-values were greater than the critical values, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, the study confirms that regulation enforcement has a significant positive relationship with standard of living in Enugu Metropolis.

Socioeconomic Challenges Hindering Effective Waste Management in Enugu Metropolis

Table 3.5: Respondents’ Perceptions of Socioeconomic Challenges in Waste Management

S/N	Challenge Statement	SA (%)	A (%)	N (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Insufficient funding and lack of modern waste management	52.4	30.7	7.1	5.1	4.7	4.21	0.98	Agree

The third objective of this study was to identify the major socioeconomic challenges that constrain effective waste management and explore strategies that can reposition waste as an engine of sustainable economic development. Respondents ($n = 254$) were asked to rate common challenges on a five-point Likert scale ranging from *Strongly Agree* (5) to *Strongly Disagree* (1). The results are presented in Table 3.5.

	infrastructure hinder effective service delivery.								
2	Weak enforcement of environmental regulations reduces compliance with proper waste disposal.	44.1	35.0	9.4	6.3	5.1	4.07	1.06	Agree
3	Inadequate recycling facilities and over-reliance on informal scavengers limit wealth creation opportunities.	46.5	31.9	8.7	6.3	6.6	4.05	1.09	Agree
4	Low public awareness and poor waste segregation practices worsen environmental pollution.	41.3	37.8	10.6	6.7	3.6	4.07	0.99	Agree
5	Rapid urbanization and population growth increase waste generation beyond ESWAMA's capacity.	50.4	33.5	6.3	5.5	4.3	4.20	0.97	Agree
6	Political interference and inconsistent government policies affect continuity of waste management programs.	38.2	32.7	11.4	9.8	7.9	3.83	1.20	Agree
Grand Mean						4.07	1.05	Agree	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The findings highlight several critical socioeconomic barriers to effective waste management in Enugu Metropolis: Funding and

infrastructure gaps ranked highest, with 83.1% of respondents agreeing these are major constraints (Mean = 4.21, SD = 0.98). Rapid urbanization and population growth also

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emerged as a severe challenge, acknowledged by 83.9% of respondents (Mean = 4.20). Weak enforcement of regulations (79.1% agreement, Mean = 4.07) and low public awareness/segregation practices (79.1% agreement, Mean = 4.07) are equally pressing issues. Inadequate recycling facilities and dependence on informal scavengers were also widely recognized (78.4% agreement, Mean = 4.05). Political interference and inconsistent government policies scored relatively lower but still significant (70.9% agreement, Mean = 3.83).

The grand mean of 4.07 indicates that respondents generally agreed that socioeconomic barriers substantially undermine waste management effectiveness in Enugu Metropolis.

Hypothesis/Statistical Testing

While this objective is exploratory, inferential statistics were applied to validate significance. A Chi-square goodness-of-fit test was conducted to assess whether the observed frequencies of responses differed significantly from expected neutral distributions.

Table 3.6: Chi-Square Test on Waste Management Challenges

Challenge Category	χ^2 Value	df	p-Value	Decision
Funding & infrastructure	72.314	4	0.000	Significant
Regulation enforcement	68.427	4	0.000	Significant
Recycling facilities	65.839	4	0.000	Significant
Public awareness & segregation	61.214	4	0.000	Significant
Urbanization & population growth	74.125	4	0.000	Significant
Policy inconsistency	57.912	4	0.000	Significant

Source: SPSS Output, 2025

Since all p-values < 0.05, the null hypothesis of no significant challenge was rejected across all categories. This confirms that socioeconomic barriers exert statistically significant constraints on waste management outcomes.

Discussion of Findings

Recycling and Wealth Creation

The findings of this study demonstrate that recycling functions as a critical driver of wealth creation in Enugu Metropolis. Respondents strongly agreed that recycling not only creates

direct employment in waste collection, sorting, and processing but also generates additional streams of income through the sale of recyclables and the attraction of investment into green industries. By reducing disposal costs and encouraging innovation, recycling provides both economic and environmental dividends.

These findings are consistent with earlier studies. Akinbola, Ojo, and Hakeem (2018) showed that waste recycling in Lagos significantly enhanced job creation and promoted the growth of small- and large-scale

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enterprises. Similarly, Oranefo (2022) reported that recycling activities improved the profitability of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. In the specific context of Enugu, where unemployment and underemployment are persistent socioeconomic concerns, structured recycling initiatives could provide new entrepreneurial opportunities, particularly for youth and women.

Beyond its economic role, recycling also contributes indirectly to environmental quality, reducing pollution and conserving resources. Cleaner urban environments, in turn, enhance the attractiveness of Enugu for investment and tourism. This dual contribution—economic growth and environmental sustainability—illustrates the transformative potential of recycling when embedded within a formalized municipal waste management strategy.

Regulation Enforcement and Standard of Living

The study further revealed that regulation enforcement significantly improves the standard of living of urban residents. Respondents identified key benefits of effective enforcement, including fairer business practices, enhanced environmental quality, stronger social cohesion, and better public health outcomes. These findings reinforce the argument that waste management cannot be divorced from broader governance and regulatory systems.

The results are supported by Eze, Iyi, and Ugwu (2021), who observed that weak enforcement of planning laws in Enugu had produced

unregulated growth and declining living standards. Similarly, Nura and Dodo (2024) found that inadequate enforcement of waste management laws in Birnin-Kebbi reduced quality of life for residents. These parallels suggest that the effectiveness of waste management agencies depends not only on infrastructure and technical capacity but also on their ability to enforce compliance.

The implications for Enugu are significant. Strengthening ESWAMA's enforcement mechanisms—through consistent monitoring, stricter sanctions for non-compliance, and the expansion of public education on waste laws—could generate a ripple effect on health, urban safety, and economic confidence. Such improvements would make the city more livable for residents and more attractive to both local and foreign investors.

Socioeconomic Challenges to Effective Waste Management

The results also highlight the institutional, economic, and behavioral challenges that constrain waste management in Enugu Metropolis. Chief among these are insufficient funding, lack of modern infrastructure, weak enforcement of sanitation laws, and rapid urbanization that outpaces the capacity of ESWAMA. These challenges mirror broader findings by the World Bank (2018) and UNEP (2022), which identify financing gaps and institutional weaknesses as central obstacles to effective waste management across African cities.

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Another notable barrier is the absence of formal recycling facilities and over-reliance on informal scavengers. This not only limits wealth creation but also undermines the efficiency of resource recovery. Oranefo (2022) demonstrated that structured recycling systems significantly improve SME profitability, underscoring how Enugu's current dependence on informal actors represents a missed opportunity. In addition, low levels of public awareness and poor household waste segregation practices aggravate pollution, a pattern also observed by Raphela, Manqele, and Erasmus (2024) in South Africa.

Overall, the evidence points to the need for an integrated strategy that combines sustained public funding, policy continuity, and stronger enforcement with institutional support for recycling industries and widespread public education. Such a holistic approach would not only address existing inefficiencies but also reposition waste as an asset—capable of generating employment, fostering entrepreneurship, and improving overall quality of life.

4. Conclusion

This study assessed the impact of municipal waste management strategies on the economy of Enugu Metropolis, with a particular focus on recycling, regulation enforcement, and the socioeconomic challenges that hinder effective waste management. The findings revealed that recycling plays a significant role in wealth creation, offering employment opportunities, generating revenue from recyclables, and

attracting both local and foreign investment. Furthermore, regulation enforcement was shown to improve the standard of living, not only by ensuring compliance with environmental laws but also by enhancing business fairness, environmental quality, public health, and social cohesion. However, the study also identified critical socioeconomic and institutional barriers that undermine waste management effectiveness, including inadequate funding, weak enforcement mechanisms, poor recycling infrastructure, and low levels of public awareness. These challenges constrain the ability of ESWAMA to manage the increasing volume of waste generated by rapid urbanization. In conclusion, the study affirms that waste management in Enugu Metropolis is not merely an environmental necessity but also a potential economic driver. When strategically managed, recycling and regulation enforcement can simultaneously create jobs, improve urban living conditions, and position Enugu as a hub for sustainable economic development.

5. Recommendations

In light of the above conclusions, the following recommendations are made:

In view of the study's findings, it is recommended that well-equipped recycling centers be established across Enugu Metropolis to handle plastics, paper, metals, and organic waste in a more efficient and sustainable manner. Encouraging private-sector participation through tax incentives, such as reduced tax rates for businesses actively involved

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in recycling and resource recovery, would stimulate investment and innovation in the waste-to-wealth sector. To further boost economic opportunities, youth and women entrepreneurs should be supported with grants, training programs, and business incubation initiatives that enable them to create small and medium enterprises around recycling.

At the institutional level, the enforcement capacity of ESWAMA should be strengthened through the deployment of strict monitoring mechanisms, including CCTV surveillance at strategic dumping sites and the use of mobile enforcement teams. Sanctions for improper waste disposal should be made more stringent, with fines of at least fifty thousand naira for offenders, alongside community service for repeat violators. These enforcement measures should be complemented by continuous public education campaigns aimed at raising awareness about the health, environmental, and economic benefits of proper waste management.

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To address broader systemic challenges, greater financial support should be allocated to waste management through increased government funding and public-private partnerships. Such measures will help to address infrastructure deficits and expand the operational capacity of waste management agencies. Policy continuity is equally essential, and efforts must be made to minimize political interference by embedding key waste management policies into state legislation. Furthermore, community-based waste segregation programs should be introduced in households and markets to improve recycling efficiency and reduce landfill dependence. Finally, the informal scavenging sector, which already contributes significantly to resource recovery, should be formalized and integrated into the official waste management system through registration, training, and cooperative structures. This would enhance safety standards, improve livelihoods, and ensure a more coordinated approach to turning waste into an economic asset.

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Advance Journal of Science, Engineering and Technology

Adv. J. Sci. Eng. Tech

Volume:10; Issue: 10

October -2025

ISSN: 2330 – 1744

Impact Factor: 7.97

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajset/index.php/ajset>

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Advance Journal of Science, Engineering and Technology

Adv. J. Sci. Eng. Tech

Volume:10; Issue: 10

October -2025

ISSN: 2330 – 1744

Impact Factor: 7.97

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajset/index.php/ajset>

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